

AN INTERDISCIPLINARY HANDS-ON APPROACH TO PHYSICS TEACHING BY USING SIMULATION PROGRAMS AND COMPUTER CONTROLLED SENSORS

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Abstract

New methodologies in science teaching attribute a fundamental role to student's participation in their own learning process. To attain this objective several strategies can be used. A common characteristic is their emphasis in stressing student's motivation as a fundamental key to the success of new didactic approaches. Simple hands-on experiments and the use of simulation tools are an appealing alternative to traditional lessons. These were the guidelines for a project launched by the Portuguese Ministry of Science and Technology to increase the experimental teaching of scientific subjects and motivate students and teachers to improve their classes by performing and developing a set of simple experiments.

I-Introduction

In this communication we describe a project entitled "Modelling and Experimentation in Science Teaching" (1) where an emphasis was placed in the use of modern tools such as sensors, simulation programs and the use of the Internet to provide an interdisciplinary approach to the teaching of Physics, Maths and Chemistry.

Simple, affordable experiments designed to encourage student's questions were performed using sensors for data acquisition and analysis. A new software package entitled, "Modellus" (2), designed at F.C.T, in Portugal, allowed the simulation of the experiments by simple modelling of phenomena.

Three aspects were considered and constitute the main axis of its development:

- First the need to involve student's participation by stressing the importance of hands-on experiments, performed either in the traditional way, or by using simple sensors connected to computers.
- Secondly by using simulation tools, designed in Portugal to allow the simulation of the experiment and visualisation of results in the computer screen, which permits the elaboration of simple modelling of physical phenomena.

- Thirdly, to take advantage of data analysis tools to promote an interdisciplinary approach in the teaching of Physics, Maths and Chemistry.

Prior to the development of these experiments in schools, training sessions for high school teachers were organised. These sessions consisted in several seminars that focused on the following points:

- To provide schoolteachers with some background on the use of computer controlled sensors and their operating principles.
- To demonstrate the use of the simulation package and its possibilities.
- To introduce the use of the Internet as a fundamental tool for subject research and discussion of results.

The results obtained in these seminars and their evaluation are available on the WWW at <http://phoenix.sce.fct.unl.pt/cviva/>. Some of the experiments performed will be discussed ahead.

II-Description of Sensor Experiments

The Sensor-Computer Interface

An introductory session on the sensor-computer interface allowed a more effective use of the software package that controls the sensors. This session focused on the issues concerning the signal processing from the sensor element to the main central processing unit of a computer. The distinction between the information representation on a computer (by digital signals), and the information captured by the sensor element (by analogue signals) led to the transformation process of an analogue signal into a digital one. Thus, a clearer understanding of the sampling rate, dynamic range, calibration and other measurement controls available to the student was possible.

Determination of the Concentration of a Solution

In this experiment a device called a colorimeter was used as the sensor. It consists mainly of a light source (LED) and a photo-detector. The light coming from the source passes across the coloured solution and excites the photo-detector. The higher the concentration of the solution, the higher is the amount of light absorbed and so the amount of light that reaches the photo-detector diminishes.

The absorbance of the solution is plotted as a function of concentration. Several solutions of known concentration are used to calibrate the colorimeter.

The relation obtained is a linear one and illustrates the Beer's Law. From the experimental points obtained, an extrapolation is allowed for the solution of unknown concentration.

The pH Compensation

The pH evolution in real time of an acid-base chemical reaction can be observed by repeated measurements using a pH sensor. Equal quantities of a base solution were added to the acid solution. The reaction could be enhanced by the use of pH indicators,

allowing the observation of the point of turn over.

The pH curve can be evaluated in real time and the point of inflexion could be measured for several acid-base solutions, using the available graphical tools.

Studying the Variation of Light Intensity

Using a light sensor, the students observed the light intensity of an incandescent lamp and a fluorescent lamp when using an alternated voltage supply and a direct current voltage supply. This experiment could be introduced by an explanation of the electromagnetic spectrum, and enhanced with the study of the optical sensor performance characteristics, like sensitivity and the calibration procedure. In a multidisciplinary level, the signal could be used to study periodic functions in time, leading the students to the measurement of its period and frequency.

Acoustic Interference of Sinusoidal Sound Waves.

Using one microphone, two sinusoidal function generators and 2 loudspeakers, it was possible to illustrate the sound interference phenomena verified with two similar frequencies f_1 and $f_2 = f_1 + \varepsilon$, $\varepsilon \ll f_1$. This effect can be described mathematically, by means of a sum of two sinusoidal functions with those frequencies (f_1 and f_2). A straightforward calculation, is enough to show that the resulting interference can be compared to the amplitude modulation described by $\sin(f_1 + \varepsilon/2) \sin(\varepsilon/2)$. This feature was observed in laboratory using three different ways:

- The acoustic beating that could be heard due to the low modulation frequency $\varepsilon/2$
- By connecting the microphone to an interface and using the appropriate software, the students were able to use a computer to perform frequency measurements and inspect the acoustic waveforms;
- Using the same equipment, it was possible to observe the spectrum of the signal estimated by means of a Fast Fourier Transform algorithm.

III-Further Comments

The second year of the project is running now, and the results obtained with students are not yet amenable to a statistical analysis.

So far the results obtained show that both students and teachers have reacted in a positive way to this approach.

References

1. **Project "Experimentação e Modelação no Ensino das Ciências", (Experimentation and Modelling in the Teaching of Sciences), Program "Ciência Viva", 1997-1998.**
2. **"Modellus: Using a Computational Tool to Change the Teaching and Learning of Mathematics and Science", Vitor Duarte Teodoro, UNESCO**

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